

**APPLICATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES AMONG TEACHERS IN PUBLIC
PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN WAMAKKO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA SOKOTO
STATE, NIGERIA**

By

Gumbi, Sambo Umar

sambo.umar@udusok.edu.ng Tel: 08038303425

**Department of Adult Education and Extension Services,
Faculty of Education and Extension Services
Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto**

&

Muhammad Maccido

maccidom@gmail.com

**Department of Adult Education and Extension Services,
Faculty of Education and Extension Services
Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto**

Abstract

The study employs descriptive survey research design where teachers' application of instructional strategies in public primary school in Wamakko local government education area was examined. One research objective and one research question was raised to guide the study. The population of the study comprises eighty-eight (88) public primary schools with the total number of one thousand one hundred and forty-seven (1147) classroom teachers across the local government area. stratified random Sampling technique was used in selecting the primary schools and fifty percent (50%) of eighty-eight schools across the urban and rural schools were selected given the sample of forty-four (44). Simple random sampling technique was used and in selecting the number of teachers to represent the entire population. Two hundred and ninety-one (291) primary school teachers were selected from 1147 teachers through Research Advisor (2006). Four items researcher-made checklist was used to collect data, the instrument was validated by experts in the field of curriculum, test and measurement and finally by the expert in primary education. test-re-test method was used to ensure the reliability index of 0.80 of the instrument. The researcher employed the services of six trained research assistants to administer and retrieve the instruments observed, and assessed base on their lesson. The data collected was analyzed using frequency counts, percentages and bar chart. The finding of the study revealed that a significant number of teachers are not utilizing problem-solving and field-trip method of teachings in public primary schools. The study recommended that, Teachers should be provided with the training and workshops on effective implementation of field trip and problem-solving methods to enhance their teaching skills and confidence.

Keywords: Instructional strategies, Teachers, Demonstration, Field-trip, role-play, play-way and discussion methods

Introduction

Primary school is designed to transform and meet the demand of the society, parent send their children to school to be taught by teachers in a formal way. Primary school as a formal organization requires a designed curriculum, conducive learning environment, trained teachers who possess the technical know-how on how to impart knowledge to these children. These technical know-hows are the techniques, ways, skills methods and strategies. These strategies differ in different ways, and can be used where they are suitable, applicable and relevant to subject matter.

Therefore, Teaching strategies are techniques used by teachers to help pupils become independent and strategic learners. Instructional strategies are ways by which educational aims are translated to practice as well as reality. In relation to this, Instructional strategies are the additional ways or techniques teachers use to encourage pupils to learn and become knowledgeable and independent thinkers to promote active learning opportunities, formative and summative assessment, peer interaction and project-based. Hiram, (2015). However, (Ekott, 2017) Classified instructional strategies into three namely; organizational, delivery, and management instructional strategies. Organizational instructional strategy has to do with how the instruction would be sequenced. Delivery instructional strategy has to do with the medium use and how pupils will be grouped while management instructional strategy has to do with scheduling and allocating resources at various levels. According to Marzano, Pickering & Pollock (2017), teaching strategies are technique teachers adopt, adapt or create while teaching the pupils to intensify their participation in the teaching/learning process in different ways and

this include: team teaching, personality traits, identifying similarities and differences; micro-learning, spaced repetition, or distributed practice, mobile phones, summarizing and note taking; reinforcing effort and providing recognition; homework and practice; nonlinguistic representations; cooperative learning; setting objectives and providing feedback; generating and testing hypotheses; questions, and advance organizers and Think-Pair-Share strategy.

In relation to this, Dick et al. (2015) define instructional strategies as the general components of a set of instructional materials and the procedures used with those materials to enable students' mastery of learning outcomes. In contrast, Elam (2011) argues that instructional strategies are the procedures used by instructors to show that their energies assist learners with their study efforts for each performance objective. In the same vein, Vural (2016) in Lowell and Rodriguez, (2023) alluded that an instructional method is a systematic plan of what to teach, how to teach, and what tools to use. Considering these previous descriptions, we combined key elements (i.e., activity or procedure, teaching process, with consideration of topic, materials, and students. Similarly, Instructional strategies are methods, techniques or ways use by teachers to handle pupils' individual differences, taking into cognizance their levels, age, gender, and characteristics to facilitate learning and promote academic performance and engagement in the class. In addition to this, Instructional strategies are styles and teaching skills displayed by subject teachers to arouse the interest of the pupils, maintain and enhance classroom management so that teaching and learning will take place.

In order to have a room for discussion of findings, relevant studies were empirically reviewed. Hmelo-Silver, (2004) studied the Problem-based learning: What and how do students learn? The study found that many teachers tend to focus on transmission of knowledge rather than encouraging critical thinking and problem solving in the same vein, Schoenfeld, (2013),

conducted a study on Classroom observations of teaching practices. In his research he revealed a significant number of teachers lack confidence in their ability to implement problem-solving methods. Citing lack of training and support. However, Marzano, (2007) conducted a research on the art and science of teaching: A comprehensive framework for effective instruction. Among his findings are, a significant number of primary school teachers used demonstration methods as their primary teaching approach. In relation to this, Harlen, (2013). research on Teaching science in primary schools, found that 80% of teachers relied on demonstration methods to teach complex concepts. Though finding of Kisiel, (2013). In research titled Integrating field trips into the curriculum: A survey of teachers' practices. revealed that only 12% of elementary school teachers applied field-trip as a regular method of teaching. Furthermore, a survey of Urban teachers' perspectives on fieldtrips. by Rivkin, (2014), revealed that a significant number of teachers reported never taking their students on field trips due to safety concerns. In another study conducted by Brophy, (2013). titled Teaching social studies in the elementary grades. revealed that a significant number of social studies teachers used role-play method to teach historical events and cultural practices. Moreover, in a study of language teachers conducted by Nunan, (2003) conducted research on the impact of role-play on Language learning. System, found that 80% of them applied role-play to teach communication skills. In another study conducted by Clements, (2017) in an observational study of classroom teaching practices found that a significant number of teachers applied play-way methods to teach Math concepts. In a study relevant to this, Kuhl, (2015), revealed that 75% of primary school teachers used play-way method of teaching.

Statement of the problem

Pupils' poor academic performance is triggered by the teachers' inability to deliver their lessons effectively. There is no doubt the selection and utilization of instructional strategies is crucial in realizing instructional objectives. This is because it is expected that teaching in primary school should be exploratory, participatory and experimental. This can only be possible when teachers are competent and skillful enough to select the appropriate and suitable method of teaching at each level of primary school. The rate at which teachers demonstrate inefficiency, ineffectiveness and incompetence in teaching is alarming. It is assumed, agreed and stated in the National policy on Education that the minimum qualification to teach in primary school is NCE. This is because it is expected that any teacher who pass through college of education is competent enough to handle the individual differences among the pupils, select and utilize the relevant instructional materials, instructional strategies for the lesson in primary school. As a result of this, the study seeks to investigate the application of instructional strategies among the public primary schools' teachers in Wamakko Local Government, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to examined the Instructional Strategies among teachers in Primary Schools in Wamakko Local Government Sokoto State, Nigeria while the specific objective were to;

examine the instructional strategies commonly used by teachers in public primary school?

Research Questions

The following question was raised to guide the study:

what instructional strategies are most commonly used by teachers in public primary school?

Methodology

The research employed descriptive research design. The justification for using this design was that, it describes and interprets what is and seeks to find out the things that are evident, or trends that are developing. The population of this study comprised all teachers of public primary schools in Wamakko local Government area, there are eighty-eight (88) public primary schools with the total number of one thousand one hundred and forty-seven (1147) classroom teachers across the local government area. among the teachers are males and females, from different tribes, with different educational background, qualification, socio-economic status, age and teaching experience. Stratified random Sampling technique was used in selecting the primary schools this is because some schools are located in urban and rural areas in the local government. Therefore, proportionate sampling technique was used where fifty percent (50%) of eighty-eight schools across the urban and rural schools were selected given the sample of forty-four (44) Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the number of teachers to represent the entire population. Two hundred and ninety- one (291) primary school teachers were selected from 1147 teachers through Research Advisor (2006). Four items researcher-made checklist was used to collect data, the instrument was designed to examine and observed the application of instructional strategies in the class. Four rating scale of often. not often, Rarely, and Never was used to show the level of usage of instructional strategies by teachers in primary schools. The instrument was validated by experts in the field of Curriculum, Test and Measurement and finally by the expert in Primary Education in the Department of Adult Education and Extension Services, Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. Test-re-test method was used to ensure the reliability of the instrument. A considerable number of teachers were taken in different schools out of the sample size and the instrument was tested to ensure the reliability index of 0.80 through Chronbach Alpha. The researcher employed the

of six trained research assistants to administer and retrieve the instruments. The researcher will visit eight schools, while the six trained research assistants visited six schools each making the total number of forty-four (44) schools. The researcher visited the selected schools with a letter of introduction to collect data the respondent with the help of six trained research assistants, the researcher met with the head of schools and explained the mission and thereafter solicit the cooperation of the teachers. The researcher explained to the participants that their responses will be treated with strict confidentiality and for the purpose of the research only. The respondents after being satisfied with the explanation of the researcher were observed, and assessed base on their lesson. The researcher and trained research assistants later retrieved the instruments for analysis. The data collected was analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and bar chart

Results and Findings

The data presented shows how significant number of teachers ignored the use of problem-solving method of teaching during their lesson delivery. This is in line with the finding of (Hmelo-Silver, 2004) who believe that many teachers tend to focus on transmission of

knowledge rather than encouraging critical thinking and problem solving in the same vein, Schoenfeld, 2013, found that a significant number of teachers lack confidence in their ability to implement problem-solving methods. Citing lack of training and support.

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The chart presented above shows how a significant number of teachers apply demonstration method of teaching during their lesson. This is in relation with the finding of Marzano, (2007) that a significant number of primary school teachers used demonstration methods as their primary teaching approach. In relation to this, Harlen, (2013). Found that 80% of teachers relied on demonstration methods to teach complex concepts.

From the data presented above, it is believed that none of the teachers utilized field trip method in primary school. This finding concurred with the finding of Kisiel, (2013). Who believed that only 12% of elementary school teachers applied field-trip as a regular method of teaching. Furthermore, a survey of teachers in urban schools by Rivkin, (2014) found that a significant number of teachers reported never taking their students on field trips due to safety concerns.

From the above presentation, it is believed that a significant number of teachers (270)

utilizes role- Play method, while only (11) teachers used role play method without considering its suitability and relevance. This is in consonant with the finding of Brophy, (2013). Revealed that a significant number of social studies teachers used role-play method to teach historical events and cultural practices. Moreover, in a study of language teachers conducted by Nunan, (2003) found that 80% of them applied role-play to teach communication skills.

Based on the chart above, a significant number of teachers (290) in primary school apply play way Method of teaching, this is due to the fact that they believe it can fit into any topic and suit the learners. This is in line with Clements, (2017) in an observational study of classroom teaching practices found that a significant number of teachers applied play-way methods to teach Math concepts. In a study relevant to this, Kuhl, (2015), revealed that 75% of primary school teachers used play-way method of teaching.

Summary of findings

Based on this study, primary school teachers predominantly use interactive and engaging instructional strategies, with play-way method, role-play, and demonstration method being highly utilized, showing a strong emphasis on hands-on learning, social skills development, and visual aids. On the flip side, field-trip method and problem-solving method are not widely used suggesting teachers might face challenges like logistical constraints or limited resources, and might need extra support or training to incorporate them effectively

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study revealed a significant trend in the application of instructional strategies among primary school teachers, highlighting a strong preference for interactive and engaging methods. The overwhelming high utilization of play-way, role-play, and demonstration methods underscores the importance of hands-on learning, social skills, development, and visual aids in primary education. Conversely, the remarkably low utilization of field trip and problem solving methods suggest a gap in the implementation of experiential and critical thinking-based approaches. This disparity may be attributed to various factors, including resource constraints, logistical challenges, or limited teacher training. To enhance the quality of primary education, it is essential to address these gaps and provide teachers with the necessary support and resources to effectively integrate a diverse range of instructional strategies, ultimately fostering a more comprehensive and inclusive learning environment

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that Teachers should be provided with the training and workshops on effective implementation of field trip and problem-solving methods to enhance their teaching skills and confidence

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